

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Jeunay****FIRST NAME: Mackendy****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to display actual information below:**

I applied U.S. conventions for grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The style rule follows Turabian/Chicago parenthetical and in-text references.

I used Zotero to insert references.

I used Grammarly Pro.

According to Grammarly Pro, my plagiarism rate is xx%.

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. Which of the following options best reflects the core academic function of essay writing as emphasized in ACA-401D?
- Communicate evidence-based responses to research hypotheses through structured reasoning and critical synthesis.¹**
 - Express individual viewpoints with persuasive impact and smooth style.
 - Engage readers mainly through narrative techniques that enhance the appeal of the text.
 - Compile and report existing scholarship without engaging in interpretation or critique.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1* (Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024), 7.

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2. According to Turabian, what is the primary scholarly reason for citing sources in academic writing?

Ensure intellectual integrity and improve research credibility through open engagement with contemporary scholarship.²

Recognize the impact of existing literature, even if you do not concur with it.

Show consistency with contemporary theoretical views in the field.

Offer comprehensive context for readers who are not acquainted with the subject.

3. What does Sampson identify as the key factor affecting the overall validity of dissertation research?

The clarity and specificity of the research question anchor the entire methodological design.³

The coordination between the conceptual framework and the data analysis strategy.

The utilization of recognized statistical methods that adhere to disciplinary norms.

The adherence to the formatting and submission guidelines throughout the process is essential.

4. In qualitative dissertation research, what do Bloomberg and Volpe consider crucial for achieving methodological coherence and maintaining the integrity of the study's design?

² Kate L. Turabian, *A manual for writers of research papers, theses, and dissertations: Chicago style for students and researchers* (Chicago and London: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 139-140.

³ James P. Jr. Sampson, *A guide to quantitative and qualitative dissertation research* (Florida: Florida State University, 2017), 16-17.

- Establishing coherence among the research problem, purpose statement, and research questions.**⁴
 - Applying multiple distinct theoretical frameworks.
 - Crafting an engaging dissertation title to draw in readers.
 - Focusing on data collection rather than conceptual clarity in the early stages.

- 5. How does the English style guide of the European Commission reconcile the need for institutional accuracy with the demand for linguistic accessibility in a multilingual setting?
 - Provide practical conventions standardizing EU English usage while maximizing clarity, simplicity, and accessibility in a multilingual environment.**⁵
 - Implement rigorous stylistic consistency solely by legal drafting standards.
 - Promote British literary standards while allowing national institutions to adjust accordingly.
 - Emphasize particular terminology and institutional references rather than a broad understanding.

- 6. Why is integrating creative and critical thinking essential in PhD-level academic writing?

⁴ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing your qualitative dissertation: A roadmap from beginning to end* (Los Angeles: SAGE, 2019), 235.

⁵ European Commission. *English style guide: A handbook for authors and translators in the European Commission* (European Commission, 2021), 4-5.

- It fosters the development of original perspectives while ensuring those ideas are analytically assessed, logically structured, and supported by evidence.⁶**
 - It accommodates longer texts and more complex vocabulary, enhancing the perceived scholarly weight of the essay.
 - Creative thinking alone offers enough originality to meet academic expectations.
 - Keeping creative and critical thinking separate helps maintain logical neutrality and minimizes potential bias.
7. Why is articulating a research problem, rather than merely identifying a topic, considered essential in scholarly research?
- A research problem identifies a precise question with an unknown answer that holds importance for a specific academic audience.⁷**
 - It enables researchers to concentrate mainly on descriptive reporting instead of argumentative analysis.
 - It allows the writer to develop a literature review emphasizing comprehensiveness rather than relevance.
 - It simplifies the writing process by enabling the researcher to organize ideas without encountering conceptual uncertainty.
8. According to Turabian's discussion of question-driven inquiry, what distinguishes experienced scholars' research practices from novice researchers

⁶ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, [9](#).

⁷ Kate L. Turabian, [28-29](#).

Deleted: *ACA-401/ACA-401D coursepack: Period 1* (Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024), 9.

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Experienced researchers use guiding questions to filter and interpret evidence throughout the research process, while novices often collect information without a clear analytical purpose.⁸

Experienced researchers begin with a solid hypothesis and maintain focus on their direction, while novices can be easily swayed by the data they encounter.

Experienced researchers see questions as static starting points, while novice researchers continuously refine their questions.

Experienced researchers initially gather extensive background notes and then pose questions during the writing stage, while novices tend to rely on questions too soon.

9. What is the primary purpose of the methodology chapter in a qualitative dissertation, as emphasized by Philip Adu?

Provide a clear and comprehensive rationale for the research design, data collection, sampling, and data analysis methods.⁹

Advocate for the social significance of the research findings.

Describe the researcher's journey and challenges during the study.

Summarize the literature review and the theoretical framework supporting the study.

⁸ Ibid., 26.

⁹ Philip Adu, *Conducting qualitative research: Writing the methodology chapter* (YouTube, April 27, 2025), 1 hr., 5 min., <https://youtu.be/KRHvxY3N708>.

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10. What key factors does Nathanael Warren emphasize about utilizing Microsoft Word's citation tools for academic referencing?

- Using Word's built-in citation manager enhances accuracy and saves time; however, some citation styles may be outdated, and automatic footnote generation is not fully supported for Chicago-style references.¹⁰**
- Microsoft Word offers fully updated citation styles and automatically generates footnotes, ideally for all formats.
- Microsoft Word supports citing sources only from online databases.
- Microsoft Word's citation tools remove the need to manage any citations manually.

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No bullets or numbering

¹⁰ Nathanael Warren, *Managing and citing sources using Microsoft Word* (YouTube, Apr. 27, 2025), 7:01 min., <https://youtu.be/XeYWGby04k&t=5s>.

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